

PREVALENCE OF HIGH BLOOD PRESSURE AND QUALITY OF LIFE IN CRF PATIENTS IN KIDNEY CENTRE HAYATABAD PESHAWAR

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Abstract

Background:

High blood pressure is very frequent in patients with renal disease and its prevalence increases as chronic renal failure (CRF) progresses this is also a big issue for renal patients. The majority of patients starting renal replacement therapy were reported to have suffered from high blood pressure. The prevalence of high blood pressure in renal patients depends fundamentally on the degree of the renal failure and the type of nephropathy, but varies also as in essential HTN, with age, sex and body mass index. Evidence shows that high blood pressure is a risk factor in the progression of CRF. We will find out the percentage of prevalence of high blood pressure in the kidney Centre Hayat Abad medical Complex Peshawar and to identify its main causes. This study will show the correct results to estimate of prevalence among the population (renal diseases patients) of Peshawar Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Pakistan.) Moreover chronic kidney disease and hypertension both are now being recognized as a major public health problem that is threatening to reach epidemic proportions over the next decades (lysaght, 2002).

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of this study is:

- To know the prevalence of high blood pressure and quality of life among kidney failure patients
- To identify the factors that influence the prevalence of high blood pressures among renal failure patients

Sample Technique: convenient sampling technique were used to collect data in which Measurements of blood pressure Semi structure questionnaire were used.

METHODS:

The quantitative design is used to explore the reason for why the prevalence of blood pressure is high among kidney failure patients

A cross sectional study was conducted at institute of kidney centre in government hospital in Hayatabad Peshawar Pakistan by using questionnaire and direct interviewing with chronic renal patients, in addition to using medical record. In this study we the take data from 50 patients (male 25+25 female). We also taken their blood pressure readings by using spignomenometer and stethoscope and recorded them in the questioners form moreover we give preference to previous blood pressure family histories of our target population.

Introduction:

Every human being needs nutrients and oxygen for performing its daily activities. These nutrients and oxygen are absorbs in the blood from the external environment, moreover the blood supplies these nutrients and oxygen to the body. To provide these needed material to the body need some pressure to push these material through blood. Heart applies some force to push the blood towards all over the body. Moreover, this force is also come on the wall of the vessels which is called blood pressure. Blood pressure means the pressure of the blood in the blood vessels exerts against the walls of the blood vessels, when the human heart pumps out the blood normally. While Hypertension means high blood pressure (James PA, Oparil S, Carter BL, 2014) when an increase in the amount of the pressure of blood in the blood vessels is called high blood pressure. The factors which may be involved in this process higher blood volume due to the presence of extra fluid in the blood vessels and blood also. Which causes that are narrow, stiff, or clogged. Blood pressure is the force of blood pushing against blood vessel walls as the heart pumps out blood. Blood pressure test results are written with two numbers separated by a slash. For example, a health care provider will write a blood pressure result as 120/80. A health care provider will say this blood pressure result as "120 over 80." The top number is called the systolic pressure and represents the pressure as the heart beats and pushes blood through the blood vessels. The bottom number is called the diastolic pressure and represents the pressure as blood vessels relax between heartbeats. Most people without chronic health conditions have a normal blood pressure if it stays below 120/80. Prehypertension is a systolic pressure of 120 to 139 or a diastolic pressure of 80 to 89. High blood pressure is a systolic pressure of 140 or above or a diastolic pressure of 90 or above. People should talk with their health care provider about their individual blood pressure goals and how often they should have their blood pressure checked.

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Results:

In this results the prevalence rate has been seen which is 34% patients ages are in category one which is 17 years to 37 years. 42% of patients have age between 38 to 57 years and 24% patients have age is between 58 to 87 years. The increase number of patients have seen in between 38 to 57 years noted. In addition the frequency of marital status is 92% married and only 8% patients unmarried because in 50 sample 44 married and 6 unmarried. This is because CRF mostly occurs in old age as we see in age frequency most of the patient have CRF ages were above 30 years. In Pakistan the people get married in young age before 25 years. The cultural values has great effect on variables age is variable so if we decrease the age the disease will decrease in %

and if we increases the age the prevalence of CRF disease will also increase there is a great relation among ages of the patient and CRF. The prevalence of literacy 70% patient are illiterates and only 30% patient are literate The distribution of diseases prevalence rate is 22% of patients are only with CRF disease 58% of patients have CRF and HTN also and 20% of the patients suffering from CRF HTN and Diabetics also we divided them in three categories .in this study the prevalence of diagnosed patients before kidney failure was 76% of patients diagnosed before their disease (chronic renal failure) as hypertensive by Doctors or any other health care professional and 24% of patients did not diagnosed by any one before occurring kidney disease this is due to less awareness of the patients because they did not visit to doctor clinic and did not think to check their blood pressure level either it is high or not. After CRF they came to know that they have high blood pressure. Before kidney failure the prevalence is very high in chronic renal failure.56% patient think that job stress is also one of the major cause of high blood pressure but on other hand 44% patient told that job stress have no role in the high blood pressure.76% of patients have recorded high blood pressure at the time of data collection while the 24% of the patients have recorded normal blood pressure readings. Criteria of hypertension All the renal failure patients will be included who are admitted in the nephrology department adult male or female who have high blood pressure (SBP>140mmhg/DBP>90mmhg) or have been diagnosed as hypertension.64% of patients are checking their blood pressure reading at home but 36% of patients are not checking their readings of blood pressure. 60% patients agreed that Doctors advised them to check regularly at home but 40% answered that no body advised them to check blood pressure at home regularly. In this data 86% of patients agreed that high blood pressure have great effect on their kidney disease. High blood pressure have great role in kidney failure most of the patient accept that the renal failure main cause is the high blood pressure. While only 14% told that high blood pressure have no effect on kidney failure.68% of patients are doing exercise on daily basis and regularly but the 32% of patients are not doing any physical activity or exercise in daily life. 60% of patient have financial issues but 40% told that they have no financial issue in this data 94% of patients agreed that life style become change after high blood

pressure and great effect on their lifestyle but only 6% patient told that due to high blood pressure there is no any effect on life style. 66% of patients have other diseases which relates to blood pressure and 34% patients told that they don't have any other disease which we can relate with the high blood pressure. In this data the 72% of patients have family history of hypertension while the 28% patient have no family history of hypertension.

Conclusion

Prevalence of hypertension, with its high burden of CRF risk factors, represents an important public health concern. As the prevalence of high blood pressure present in the CRF patients. Moreover hypertension have great effect on the lifestyle of these patients. The identification of an individual with hypertension should alert the practitioners to a large underlying burden of potentially modifiable hypertension risk factors. The study showed a significant association between a number of CRF risk factors and hypertension, such CRF risk factors include hypertension, diabetic mellitus, and increased total cholesterol, triglycerides, LDL, and decreased HDL, physical inactivity, stress. This positive association was shown in all patient of hypertension and chronic

Introduction chapter 1:

Every human being needs nutrients and oxygen for performing its daily activities. These nutrients and oxygen are absorbs in the blood from the external environment, moreover the blood supplies these nutrients and oxygen to the body. To provide these needed material to the body need some pressure to push these material through blood. Heart applies some force to push the blood towards all over the body. Moreover, this force is also come on the wall of the vessels which is called blood pressure. Blood pressure means the pressure of the blood in the blood vessels exerts against the walls of the blood vessels, when the human heart pumps out the blood normally. While Hypertension means high blood pressure (James PA, Oparil S, Carter BL, 2014) when an increase in the amount of the pressure of blood in the blood vessels is called high blood pressure. The factors which may be involved in this process higher blood volume due to the presence of extra fluid in the blood vessels and blood also. Which causes that are narrow, stiff, or clogged. Blood pressure is the force of blood pushing against blood

vessel walls as the heart pumps out blood. Blood pressure test results are written with two numbers separated by a slash. For example, a health care provider will write a blood pressure result as 120/80. A health care provider will say this blood pressure result as “120 over 80.” The top number is called the systolic pressure and represents the pressure as the heart beats and pushes blood through the blood vessels. The bottom number is called the diastolic pressure and represents the pressure as blood vessels relax between heartbeats. Most people without chronic health conditions have a normal blood pressure if it stays below 120/80. Prehypertension is a systolic pressure of 120 to 139 or a diastolic pressure of 80 to 89. High blood pressure is a systolic pressure of 140 or above or a diastolic pressure of 90 or above. People should talk with their health care provider about their individual blood pressure goals and how often they should have their blood pressure checked.

This thesis focuses on one of the most common health problem in both developed and developing countries, namely chronic renal failure (CRF) which is a term used when kidney reaches a complete, or almost complete failure to function; kidneys can no longer remove wastes, regulate and concentrate urine (Usami T, et al., 2000).

There are two kidneys in human body which are bean-shaped organs, each about the size of a fist of individual. Both kidneys are located just below the rib cage, one on each side of the spinal cord. Every day, the both kidneys filter about 125 to 150 quarts of blood to produce about 1 to 2 quarts of urine in the body, composed of wastes and extra fluid. (Radao N, Lono J, Gome F Spain 2001)

The urine flows from the kidneys to the bladder through tubes called ureters. The bladder function is to stores urine. When the bladder become empty, urine flows out of the body through a tube called the urethra, located at the bottom of the bladder. In men the urethra is long, while in women it is short. Kidneys work at the very complex and microscopic level. The kidney is not one large filter. Each kidney is made up of about a million filtering units called nephrons. Each nephron filters a small amount of blood. The nephron includes a filter, called the glomerulus, and a tubule. The nephrons work through a two-step process. The glomerulus lets fluid and waste products pass through it; however, it prevents blood cells and large molecules, mostly proteins, from passing. The filtered fluid then passes

through the tubule, which sends needed minerals back to the bloodstream and removes wastes. The final product becomes urine. High blood pressure can damage blood vessels in the kidneys, reducing their ability to work properly. When the force of blood flow is high, blood vessels stretch so blood flows more easily. Eventually, this stretching scars and weakens blood vessels throughout the body, including those in the kidneys. If the kidneys' blood vessels are damaged, they may stop removing wastes and extra fluid from the body. Extra fluid in the blood vessels may then raise blood pressure even more, creating a dangerous cycle. High blood pressure is the second leading cause of kidney failure in the United States after diabetes, as illustrated in Figure 1.2 In addition, the rate of kidney failure due to high blood pressure increased 7.7 percent from 2000 to 2010.

(Source: Health, United States, 2011: table 51. End-stage renal disease patients, by selected characteristics: United States, selected years 1980–2010. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention website.

www.cdc.gov/nchs/data/hus/2011/051.pdf External Link Disclaimer (PDF, 25 KB)*. Updated 2011. Accessed December 20, 2013.)

Most people with high blood pressure do not have symptoms. In rare cases, high blood pressure can cause headaches.

Chronic renal failure is the irreversible loss of kidney function. At the point where kidneys fail to sustain life, renal replacement therapy is required. Dialysis is the process of cleaning the blood and removing excess fluids artificially with a special equipment called the dialysis unit (Gregorio T, et al., 1999).

Kidney disease also does not have symptoms in the early stages. A person may have swelling called edema, which happens when the kidneys cannot get rid of extra fluid and salt. Edema can occur in the legs, feet, or ankles and less often in the hands or face. Once kidney function decreases further, symptoms in which we can include

Appetite loss .nausea, Vomiting, Drowsiness or feeling tired, Trouble concentrating, Sleep problems, Increased or decreased urination, Generalized itching or numbness, Dry skin, Headaches, Weight loss, Darkened skin, Muscle cramps, Shortness of breath, Chest pain

A health care provider diagnoses high blood pressure when multiple blood pressure tests—often repeated over several visits to a health care provider's office

(Zarbato G. Janaina L Neves D Brazil 2007) show that a systolic blood pressure is consistently above 140 or a diastolic blood pressure is consistently above 90. Health care providers measure blood pressure with a blood pressure cuff. People can also buy blood pressure cuffs at discount chain stores and drugstores to monitor their blood pressure at home. Kidney disease is diagnosed with urine and blood tests. A health care provider can help people change their diet to meet their individual needs.

Physical Activity

Regular physical activity can lower blood pressure and reduce the chances of other health problems. (Kenny. T Brazil 2013) A health care provider can provide information about how much and what kinds of activity are safe. Most people should try to get at least 30 to 60 minutes of activity most or all days of the week. A person can do all physical activity at once or break up activities into shorter periods of at least 10 minutes each. Moderate activities include brisk walking, dancing, bowling, riding a bike, working in a garden, and cleaning the house.

Body Weight

People who are overweight or obese should aim to reduce their weight by 7 to 10 percent during the first year of treatment for high blood pressure. This amount of weight loss can lower the chance of health problems related to high blood pressure. Overweight is defined as a body mass index (BMI)—a measurement of weight in relation to height—of 25 to 29. A BMI of 30 or higher is considered obese. A BMI lower than 25 is the goal for keeping blood pressure under control.⁵

Smoking

People who smoke should quit. Smoking can damage blood vessels, raise the chance of high blood pressure, and worsen health problems related to high blood pressure. People with high blood pressure should talk with their health care provider about programs and products they can use to quit smoking.

Stress

Learning how to manage stress, relax, and cope with problems can improve emotional and physical health. Some activities that may help reduce stress include exercising, practicing yoga or tai chi,

listening to music, focusing on something calm or peaceful, meditating, Points to Remember Blood pressure is the force of blood pushing against blood vessel walls as the heart pumps out blood, and high blood pressure, also called hypertension, is an increase in the amount of force that blood places on blood vessels as it moves through the body.

High blood pressure can damage blood vessels in the kidneys, reducing their ability to work properly. When the force of blood flow is high, blood vessels stretch so blood flows more easily. Eventually, this stretching scars and weakens blood vessels throughout the body, including those in the kidneys. High blood pressure is the second leading cause of kidney failure in the United States after diabetes.

A health care provider diagnoses high blood pressure when multiple blood pressure tests—often repeated over several visits to a health care provider's office—show that a systolic blood pressure is consistently above 140 or a diastolic blood pressure is consistently above 90.

Kidney disease is diagnosed with urine and blood tests.

The best way to slow or prevent kidney damage from high blood pressure is to take steps to lower blood pressure. These steps include a combination of medication and lifestyle changes, such as

Healthy eating, Physical activity, maintaining a healthy weight, quitting smoking, managing stress

No matter what the cause of the kidney disease, high blood pressure can increase damage to the kidneys. People with kidney disease should keep their blood pressure below 140/90.

Hope through Research

In recent years, researchers have learned a great deal about kidney disease. The National Institute of Diabetes and Digestive and Kidney Diseases (NIDDK) sponsors several programs aimed at understanding kidney disease and finding treatments to stop its progression.

High blood pressure is very frequent in patients with renal disease and its prevalence increases as chronic renal failure (CRF) progresses this is also a big issue for renal patients. The majority of patients starting renal replacement therapy were reported to have suffered from high blood pressure. The prevalence of high blood pressure in renal patients depends fundamentally on the degree of the renal failure and the type of nephropathy, but varies also as in essential HTN, with age, sex and body mass index.

Evidence shows that high blood pressure is a risk factor in the progression of CRF. We will find out the percentage of prevalence of high blood pressure in the kidney Centre Hayat Abad medical Complex Peshawar and to identify its main causes. This study will show the correct results to estimate of prevalence among the population (renal diseases patients) of Peshawar Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Pakistan.)

Literature review chapter 2:

We searched Google scholar engine, BMJ article, nursing article and use different kinds of books for taking content, ideas, concepts, and take idea about methodology and use this resources for our research thesis with proper citation and arranged them orderly date wise for the support of our thesis we searched and carefully read 12 to 15 article which is related to our research study review of literature in our research report justify.

Review of the literature in any research report validate need for future research and explains the subsistence and significance of the research problem in light of above clarification the review of this research report does tell the reader the significance of the problem and the gap This study is supported with comprehensive, logical recent and relevant literature. The literature was not discussed adequately and further exploration may be required for a new study. There has no risk in the study for the participants and give benefits to the participants Incidence and Prevalence of CRF worldwide:

CRF (CRF) is increasing worldwide. Renal replacement therapy and kidney transplantation are increasing burden on health systems. This condition is particularly serious in developing countries where health resources are inadequate (Stengel B .2003). Worldwide, the number of patients receiving renal replacement therapy (RRT) is estimated at more than (1.4) million, with an annual incident rate growing to 8 % (chapatti A, et al., 2005).

The average of incidence of new patients treated due to CRF in EU during years (1995) was (120) persons per million populations, ranging (68) in Finland, (163) in Germany. These figures are higher in USA with (262) person per million population, Japan (210) person per million population, but lower in Canada (140) person per million population during the same year (Berthouf F, et al 1999). In 1998, the incidence of treated 21 ESRD in Europe ranged (110) person per million population, Netherlands (192) person per million population. Higher

incidence rates were recorded in the same year in countries outside Europe, such as the USA (>300 person per million population), Japan (200) person per million population (Arikan H, et al., 2005). The reported annual incidence of patients with CRF varies widely,

Diagnosis of CRF

Diagnosis of CRF typically requires the physician's review of the patient's medical history as well as a physical examination. A patient with a history of chronic kidney disease that has progressed may be suspected of having CRF. The physical examination includes tests to determine the advancement of the kidney disease and will likely include a measurement of a patient's blood pressure. Additional tests that may be performed include the following (Goldsmith D, et al., 2007).

Function of Normal Kidney

In the human body there are two kidneys, each about the size of a fist, located on each side of the spine at the lowest level of the rib cage. Each kidney contains up to a million functioning units called nephrons. A nephron consists of a filtering unit of tiny blood vessels called a glomerulus attached to a tubule. When blood enters the glomerulus, it is filtered and the remaining fluid then passes along the tubule. In the tubule, chemicals and water are either added to or removed from this filtered fluid according to our body needs (Hasslacher C, et al., 1999)

Causes of CRF:

CRF has many causes that varies from one patient to another. The key risk factors for chronic kidney disease are the increasing age of the population, diabetes mellitus II and hypertension. The most common causes include the following (Myrray I, 2007).

Uncontrolled hypertension can damage the kidneys over time.

- Glomerulonephritis is the inflammation and damage of the filtration system of the kidney and can cause kidney failure.
- Polycystic kidney disease is an example of a hereditary cause of chronic kidney disease where both kidneys have multiple cysts.
- Medications such as the use of some analgesics regularly over long durations of time can cause analgesic nephropathy and kidney damage.

- Atherosclerosis leading to ischemic nephropathy, can cause kidney damage.

- Obstruction of the urinary tract by stones or cancer can lead to the enlargement of the prostate and then strictures that may cause kidney damage.

Diabetes mellitus type I and type II cause diabetic nephropathy, that leads to kidney failure. Diabetes is the largest single cause of ESRD in the United Kingdom, accounting for 30– 40% of all cases (Sandra W, 2005).

- Obese American people have up to a seven times greater risk of kidney failure than non obese people, suggesting that obesity should be considered a risk factor for ESRD (Hyman C, 2006)

Heart has a blood pumping system to the body through this mechanism heart pumps blood to the different parts of the body the blood pushes against the walls of your blood vessels and arteries this force become too high what doctor call blood pressure (Pearce E 1975) p172 there is no exact cause of blood pressure but some risk factor can increase the developing chance of it like age, gender, race, family history, sedentary lifestyle, stress, diet, smoking, alcohol use etc.

Blood force is the pressure of blood in the blood vessels. Blood pressure is measured in millimeters of mercury (mm Hg). Blood pressure is recorded in two figures. For instance, 140/100 mm Hg is read as 140 over 100. The top (first) number is the systolic pressure. This is the pressure in the arteries when the heart contracts.

The bottom (second) number is the diastolic pressure. This is the pressure in the arteries when the heart rests between each heartbeat. Dr Tim Kenny (December 2013) blood pressure is a dangerous because it makes the heart work too hard due to atherosclerosis (hardening

Of the arteries). High blood pressure also can result kidney disease.

Blood pressure is checked by a machine which is called spigmomonomerer (B.P set) the cuff around the arm which cover the ¼ of arm in sitting or lying position during rest time blood pressure can be checked every time and keep record of your blood pressure because it is very important to show to your doctor or any health profession if anyone how has high blood pressure has high risk of developing C.K.D.They are related in two ways: High blood pressure is 1. a leading cause of CKD.Over time, high blood pressure can damage blood vessels throughout your body. This can reduce the blood

supply to important organs like the kidneys. High blood pressure also damages the tiny filtering units in your kidneys. As a result, the kidneys may stop removing wastes and extra fluid from your blood. The extra fluid in your blood vessels may build up and raise blood pressure even more. 2. High blood pressure can also be a complication Of CKD. Your kidneys play a key role in keeping your blood pressure in a healthy range.

Hypertension is considered one of main risk factors of CKD in Kuwait especially in old age (El-Reshaid K, et al., 1999). Diseased kidneys are less able to help regulate blood pressure. As a result, blood pressure increases. If you have CKD, high blood pressure makes it more likely that your kidney disease will get worse and you will have heart problems. Following your treatment plan and keep in your blood pressure controlled can help keep your kidney disease from getting worse and prevent heart disease.

We studied and find some information regarding patients suffering from CRF disease to answer the high blood pressure and to think about that time that may be blood pressure become high so we studied in the internet and search about the symptoms of high blood pressure which is very essential for patient knowledge and information. According to National Kidney foundation

National Kidney Foundation:

The only way to tell if your blood pressure is too high is to have it measured. High blood pressure usually causes no symptoms. That is why it has been called a “silent killer.” A single high reading may not mean you have high blood pressure. It should be confirmed on follow-up visits to your doctor or clinic. Blood pressure is measured as two numbers. The top number, or systolic blood pressure, is the pressure when your heart is beating. The bottom number, or diastolic blood pressure, is the pressure when your heart is resting between beats. A blood pressure reading of 130/80 is read as 130 over 80. Normal blood pressure in adults 18 and older is less than 120/80. People who have blood pressure between 120 and 139 for the top number, or between 80 and 89 for the bottom number, may be more likely to develop high blood pressure unless they take steps to prevent it. In general, blood pressure that stays

At 140/90 or higher is considered high. However, for People who have diabetes or CKD, a blood pressure of 130/80 or higher is considered high.

(National Kidney Disease Education Program July 2014)

A lot of researches have been done which aims to describe knowledge, awareness, and level of health, associated factors and life style among the participants. Here we study this article which we are going to discuss here the topic is

Prevalence of high blood pressure levels and associated factors among adults in southern Brazil;

The authors of this article are Giana Zarbato Longo, Janaina das Neves, Valmir Martins Luciano, Marco Aurélio Peres that did their research study at Brazil in the field work was carried out between April and September 2007.

The aim of the study is to estimate the prevalence of high blood pressure and associated factors among adults in Lages, Southern Brazil.

In this study they find out the high prevalence and the social and economic consequences of hypertension to identify the health in the people of Brazil. According their study in 2006, 17 million Brazilians presented hypertension, which represented 35% of adult individuals older than 40 years.

The author of this study did their research on arterial hypertension is associated to a family history of hypertensive disease and give touch to other factors such as overweight, insufficient physical activity, high sodium intake, smoking, abusive alcohol consumption, self-medication, use of drugs that affect the blood pressure (BP), dyslipidemia and diabetes mellitus. They describe their diagnostic criteria of hypertension is the presence of BP values $> 140/90$ mmHg, measured in at least two different times. In epidemiological studies, measurements of high BP levels estimate the prevalence of hypertension. The present study aimed at estimating the prevalence of the high BP among adults living in the urban area of the town of Lages, state of Santa Catarina, southern Brazil they did this study because there were no specific record on the prevalence of pressure levels and associated factors in the age range and the population evaluated in the study. They use cross sectional method for their study carried out in adults aged 20 to 59 years living in the urban area ($n=2,022$). The dependent variable was high levels of blood pressure ($\geq 140/90$ mmHg). Exploratory variables: sex, age, schooling, per capita family income, self-reported ethnicity, body mass index, tobacco and alcohol addiction, physical activity and

self-reported diabetes. The Chi-square test and linear trends were used to test associations between the dependent variable and the exploratory variables. They take interview from those houses that are selected for data collection as a sample size. They consider all living adults eligible for the study, at the time of data collection totaling, they arrange visits four time one visit on the end of week and other is on evening time.

They describe their exclusion criteria which is pregnant women, amputees, bedridden individuals, individuals with casts, individuals with psychiatric disorders and those who, or some reason, could not remain in the adequate position for the required measurements. For data collection they did home visits included the use of a face-to-face questionnaire, BP measurement and anthropometric measurements. To achieve the standard data they did pilot study on 30 people which is randomly selected for the study among those that were not selected for the study itself. They define the hypertension criteria the SAP >140 mmHg and/or DAP >90 mmHg for study those individuals known to be hypertensive whose regular use of anti-hypertensive medication and BP levels were elevated or not at the moment of the interview. They measure the BP levels two times before and after the questionnaire were applied and the second measurement was the one considered for the study. The measurements were carried out with the interviewee in the sitting position, with feet planted on the floor, left arm relaxed and supported on a table at the level of the heart and the palm facing upward. Electronic equipment with a digital reading system that had been adequately calibrated was used to measure the blood pressure levels Smoking was classified in three categories: non-smoker, ex-smoker and current smoker. Problems with alcohol were investigated to identify risk factors for SAH using the CAGE questionnaire. They categorized the physical activity level as active or sedentary and ask question about their health the data were entered in duplicate in the Epi-Info. After verifying the reliability of the data, the statistical analyses were carried out using the statistical package STATA version 9.0. They use Chi-square test for analysis to verify the associations between the dependent variable (pressure level) and each independent variable. The response rate was 98.6%, which corresponds to 2,022 investigated individuals, of whom 47.7% were males and 52.3% were females; the remaining 1.4% corresponds to

refusals and losses. The estimated prevalence of elevated BP levels was 33.7%. The socioeconomic and demographic variables associated with elevated BP levels were: sex, age, degree of schooling and ethnicity. Males presented a prevalence of elevated BP levels of 31.1% and females, of 38.1%. Individuals from the group with a lower degree of schooling had a prevalence that was 62% higher than those with 12 years of schooling or more. There was a dose-response association between age and the prevalence of BP levels that ranged from 16.2% among the younger individuals to 56.5% in the older group. Shows a positive association between elevated BP levels and BMI.

The prevalence ratio was 1.8 for overweight individuals and 2.9 for obese ones, when compared with individuals that had normal weight. Regarding the waist circumference, the individuals considered to be in the non-ideal category presented a higher prevalence of elevated BP levels ($p < 0.001$). The prevalence of elevated BP levels was 92% higher among the individuals that referred having diabetes mellitus, when compared to those without the disease, whereas the prevalence of the elevated BP levels was 31% higher among ex-smokers when compared to non-smokers they used studies that analyze the disease for comparison as these levels are associated with it. In observational, cross-sectional studies, the main limitations are caused by the possibility of selection bias, reverse-causality bias and the involvement of confounding factors.

The author of study defined as levels $> 140/90$ mmHg, or in the case of individuals that regularly used anti-hypertensive medication. Two BP measurements were performed at the individuals' homes and the second one was considered for the study, which is in accordance with the literature. In 2006, public policies were released to prevent hypertension and promote health among the Brazilian population. The main objective of this study is to reduce the prevalence of elevated BP levels are the increased access to primary care, the incentive of popular health education to the of the family adherence to treatment, the guarantee of an adequate diet, thus preventing overweight, obesity and smoking the find out of the main factors associated to hypertension through population-based studies and effective control strategies, combined with community education and the prioritized monitoring of individuals at high risk,

contributed to a significant decrease in mortality in almost all developed countries.

Risk Factors of CRF in literature

Diabetes Mellitus and Hypertension:

A study was conducted in Canada to determine the prevalence of CRF showed that the increases prevalence and incidence were estimated, particularly among people with diabetes mellitus. In 1996, there were (17,807) patients receiving renal replacement therapy in Canada. This number jumped to (32,952) by 2005, for a relative increase of (85%) and a mean annual increase of (5.8%)(Schaube DE, et al., 1999)

A study was conducted in UK showed that CRF is common. The main risk factor for impaired kidney function is diabetes mellitus. About (30%) of patients with diabetes II develop some degree of diabetic nephropathy. In addition, a follow-up study conducted in South Africa showed that diabetes mellitus is a major risk factor of CRF (Keeton GR, et al., 2004).

Across sectional study conducted in Egypt in order to determine the prevalence of diabetic nephropathy as a cause of CRF showed that the prevalence of diabetic nephropathy increased gradually from (8.9%) in 1996, to (14.5%) in 2001. average age of patients with diabetic nephropathy was significantly higher than other causes of patients with CRF. Mortality was also significantly higher in diabetic patients with CRF(Afifi A, et al., 2004) A retrospective analysis study conducted in Saudi Arabia to determine Risk Factors for Developing CRF. Results showed that diabetes II is the main risk factor (Al-Jiffri A, et al., 2003).

In Jordan, Another study about epidemiology of dialysis patient showed that prevalence of haemodialysis was (312) person per million population. CRF incidence in 2002 was (111) person per million population. Diabetes mellitus was leading cause of haemodialysis (29.2%) of cases (Batieha A, et al., 2007)

Another study was conduct on hypertension :This study is done by Natalia Radao, jose Lono, Francisco Gomez, Alberto Tojodor and Fernando Velderrabano in Hospital General Universitario Gregorio Maranon, Madrid, Spain in 2001. The topic is prevalence of hypertension in kidney disease they discuss the prevalence of hypertension and describe that it is the major cause of chronic kidney disease they reported that most of people did renal

transplant who have suffered from hypertension they mention the age, sex, body mass index and on the degree of renal failure high blood pressure is the risk factor of CKD. They elaborate the strict control on blood pressure, as well as reduce the cardiovascular disease they studied the prevalence of hypertension on nephrology clinic and analyses the clinical and biochemical record which show the prevalence of hypertension in renal disease patients and collect data on the use of different hypertension medicine. their sample size is 1921 diagnose patient of nephropathies patient on dialysis and renal transplant is not the part of study the criteria of blood pressure is SBP>140 and DBP >90 or required antihypertensive medicine and blood pressure reading were taken three time consecutively and renal disease is defined at least one alteration of the following Creatinine clearance (Cr <70 ml/min) proteinuria, hematuria, and other alteration of renal function. The prevalence of total hypertension patient in total sample is 60.5% depending on different neuropathy, renal vascular disease 93%, diabetic nephropathy is 87% polycystic kidney disease 74% and those with micro albuminuria 73% In this study the objectives of the authors was prevalence of hypertension in renal patients they focuses renal patients in their studies with different nephropathies. They used R-sigma Babel (Horus hardware) and results are expressed as mean of standard deviation. This study is relates to my study I learn study method, data analysis, usage of data collection tools. I also understand the prevalence of hypertension among CKD patients in Spain.

Hypertension is a main risk factor for increasing incidence of CRF in men in USA. A Follow-up study showed that Elevation of blood pressure is a strong independent risk factor of CRF (Michael J, et al., 1996)

Methodology chapter 3:

We constructed a questioner because we needed a questioner for compulsory data collection and which will accurate for our studies and by which we collect all the require data. We develop questioner after long hard work we focus on the prevalence of high blood pressure and quality of life in CRF patients. After finalizing questioner we attach a concern form with each questioner for participants. We take permission letters which we signed from our principle. One permission letter we give to Director IKD Peshawar Hayatabad. One letter we give to CNS

IKD Peshawar and individual letter to every ward in charge. After that the CNS of IKD give us orientation of different wards she introduce us with all staff. Moreover that we visit to different wards of IKD and check patients who could be included in our study. We select one ward of female and one of male patients we started questions after consent form agreement. We started data collection from the patients who are conscious oriented and relax in the ward. We take permission from the patients and their attendants if they want to participate in this study or not? After concern we ask questions based on demographic data and 20 questions based on quality of life data. We also mentioned one question for the blood pressure recording because we check blood pressure of every individual at the time of data collection. So we make a criteria for that question that either the blood pressure of the patient is still high or normal or low. We mentioned it in the area where it is coming in the questioner. Our study population is chronic renal patients so we study the quality of life also in the research like they are doing some exercise or not in the daily life. The sampling technique by which we will select the sample from our population we use convenient sampling. Because in the kidney Center Hayat Abad medical complex there are very less patient of CRF so we decided to at least to complete 60 patients. We starts the data collection in IKD in 4 ward one from ward one ward 2 and ward 3 the fourth one is private rooms of IKD. We stars visits every weekly two times on Thursday and Friday continuously we focuses on data collection for one month as we had taken permission and we mentioned in the permission letter that we will collect data in one month. We decided to take 30 males and 30 females' patients but after discussion with sir nor khan and sir Irfan we decided the sample of our study up to 50 because the kidney failure patients population is not easily available more over the patients of kidney failure in the kidney center are enough but our study population is only CRF. So we decided that 50 sample is enough for our study. In data collection

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of this study is:

- To know the prevalence of high blood pressure among kidney failure patients
- To identify the factors that influence the prevalence of high blood pressures among renal failure patients

Research Question:

Why the prevalence of blood pressure is high among CRF patients?

How the blood pressure presence is high in the CRF patients?

Study design

The quantitative design (cross sectional) will used to explore the reason for why the prevalence of blood pressure is high among kidney failure patients

.Study setting:

The study will conduct in the kidney Centre Hayatabad medical complex Peshawar .which is situated in Hayat Abad Peshawar. HMC is a government hospital. We will take patients from nephrology department of this hospital first we will take information about the renal diseases departments in kidney Centre then we will focus on those areas where our population will be easily available in a good relax environment. We will try to take 25 male adult patients and 25 female adult patients.

Subjects: The population for the study will be 50 patients according to the presence and availability of admit patients.

Sample Size: The data will be collecting from 50 patients

Sample Technique: convenient sampling technique were used to collect data in which Measurements of

Chapter 4: Results:

Demographic data results

Age results:

Table 1

Age

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	17 to 37	17	34.0	34.0	34.0
	38 to 57	21	42.0	42.0	76.0
	58 to 87	12	24.0	24.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	100.0	

blood pressure Semi structure questionnaire were used.

Recruitment:

Inclusion Criteria:

All the renal failure patients will be included who are admitted in the nephrology department adult male or female who have high blood pressure (SBP>140mmhg/DBP>90mmhg) or have been diagnosed as hypertension. Only in the ward patients will be included for the study.

Excluded criteria:

All those patients who are on dialysis and those who are in ICUs and in OPD will not be included in the study, the children and the patients less than 18years and mentally and partially disturbed patient are also excluded from the study.

Data collection:

The data was collected on semi structured questionnaire. Semi structured questioners based on the close ended question. The first part of questionnaire based on demographic data. Second part of questioner regarding hypertensive history and also we will check blood pressures and will be recorded in the research note book and also in the form of soft copy.

Data Analysis:

We will use the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) for data analysis and results.

Explanation: Tab & Fig No 1:

In this results 34% patients age is in category one which is 17 years to 37 years. 42% of patients have age between 38 to 57 years and 24% patients have age is between 58 to 87 years. The increase number of patients have seen in between 38 to 57 years noted.

sex of patient

Table: 2

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid male	25	50.0	50.0	50.0
female	25	50.0	50.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Explanation: Tab & Fig No 2:

We collect data from 50 sample which includes 50% male and 50% femal

Marital status

Table 3

marital status

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	married	46	92.0	92.0	92.0
	unmarried	4	8.0	8.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Explanation: Tab & Fig No 3:

The frequency of marital status is 92% married and only 8% patients unmarried because in 50 sample 44 married and 6 unmarried. This is because CRF mostly occurs in old age as we see in age frequency most of the patient have CRF ages were above 30 years. In Pakistan the people get married in young age before 25 years. The cultural values has great effect on variables age is variable so if we decrease the age the disease will decrease in % and if we increases the age the prevalence of CRF disease will also increase there is a great relation among ages of the patient and CRF

Table 4

Ward

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	nephro	48	96.0	96.0	96.0
	isolation	2	4.0	4.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Explanation: Tab & Fig No 4:

We collect data from the two departments one is nephrology general ward of male and female portion and the other department isolation unit of nephrology department. 96% of data we collect from nephrology general ward and only 4% data we collected from isolation department. This difference is because of the sampling technique which we use in data collection our sampling technique was convenient sampling. In the wards the patients were relax and free. So most of the data we collected from the general ward and the data from isolation department is very low because in the isolation department the CRF patients were less and if available then they were in dialysis department for dialysis.

Table 5
literate

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid littrate	15	30.0	30.0	30.0
illitrate	35	70.0	70.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Explanation: Tab & Fig No 5:

70% patient are illiterates and only 30% patient are literate in this data.

Table 6
qualification

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid primary to matric	9	18.0	18.0	18.0
intermediate	4	8.0	8.0	26.0
graduate to master	2	4.0	4.0	30.0
Illiterate	35	70.0	70.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Explanation: Tab & Fig No 6:

18% of the patient are matriculate 8% are intermediate 4% of patients have master qualification and 70% of the patients are illiterate.

Table 7

occupation

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid house wife	23	46.0	46.0	46.0
on service	22	44.0	44.0	90.0
Jobless	5	10.0	10.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Explanation: Tab & Fig No 7:

46% house wife 44% on service while jobless patients are 10% .The majority of on job population are male and they are doing jobs some are government employees and other are private workers.

residence

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid afghanistan	2	4.0	4.0	4.0
bajawar	1	2.0	2.0	6.0
Bannu	3	6.0	6.0	12.0
Buner	1	2.0	2.0	14.0
Bunnu	1	2.0	2.0	16.0
charsada	3	6.0	6.0	22.0
charsadda	1	2.0	2.0	24.0
Chatral	1	2.0	2.0	26.0
darra adam khel	1	2.0	2.0	28.0
dir	3	6.0	6.0	34.0
hangu	1	2.0	2.0	36.0
kohat	3	6.0	6.0	42.0
lakimarwat	1	2.0	2.0	44.0
mardan	7	14.0	14.0	58.0
palosai	1	2.0	2.0	60.0
peshawar	11	22.0	22.0	82.0
sawabi	4	8.0	8.0	90.0
skhakot	1	2.0	2.0	92.0
swat	1	2.0	2.0	94.0
temergara	2	4.0	4.0	98.0
upper dir	1	2.0	2.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Table 8

Diagnoses

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid CRF	11	22.0	22.0	22.0
CRF.HTN	29	58.0	58.0	80.0
CRF.HTN.DM	10	20.0	20.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Explanation: Tab & Fig No 8:

22% of patients are only with CRF disease 58% of patients have CRF and HTN also and 20% of the patients suffering from CRF HTN and Diabetics also we divided them in three categories

Table 9

Q1: Have you diagnose by any health professional or doctor that you have blood pressure?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	38	76.0	76.0	76.0
	No	12	24.0	24.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Explanation: Tab & Fig No 9:

76% of patients diagnosed before their disease (chronic renal failure) as hypertensive by Doctors or any other health care professional and 24% of patients did not diagnosed by any one before occurring kidney disease this is due to less awareness of the patients because they did not visit to doctor clinic and did not think to check their blood pressure level either it is high or not. After CRF they came to know that they have high blood pressure. Before kidney failure the prevalence is very high in chronic renal failure.

Table 10

Q 2: Are you told by your doctor about your hypertension on regular visits?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	30	60.0	60.0	60.0
	No	20	40.0	40.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Explanation: Tab & Fig No 10:

60% of patients are aware that they have blood pressure disease because during different visits Doctors told them that they have HTN and 40% patient are unaware because the doctors did not tell them in prior or they did not visit to any clinic or hospital.

Table 11

Q3: Do you feel that your job is one of the major causes of your blood pressure?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	28	56.0	56.0	56.0
	No	22	44.0	44.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Explanation: Tab & Fig No 11:

56% patient think that job stress is also one of the major cause of high blood pressure but on other hand 44% patient told that job stress have no role in the high blood pressure.

Table 12

Q4: Blood pressure of the patient at the time of data collection was?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	high blood pressure	38	76.0	76.0	76.0
	low blood pressure	12	24.0	24.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Explanation: Tab & Fig No 12:

76% of patients have recorded high blood pressure at the time of data collection while the 24% of the patients have recorded normal blood pressure readings. Criteria of hypertension All the renal failure patients will be included who are admitted in the nephrology department adult male or female who have high blood pressure (SBP>140mmhg/DBP>90mmhg) or have been diagnosed as hypertension.

Table 13

Q5: Are you taking any prescribed medicine for hypertension?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	43	86.0	86.0	86.0
	No	7	14.0	14.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Explanation: Tab & Fig No 13:

86% of patients are taking medicines for the hypertension or high blood pressure while 14% patients agreed that they are not taking any prescribe medicine for high blood pressure.

Table 14

Q6: Have you checked your blood pressure at home during rest time in last three months?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	32	64.0	64.0	64.0
	No	18	36.0	36.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Explanation: Tab & Fig No 14:

64% of patients are checking their blood pressure reading at home but 36% of patients are not checking their readings of blood pressure.

Table 15

Q7: Do you checked your blood pressure regularly and keep record?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid yes	12	24.0	24.0	24.0
no	38	76.0	76.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Explanation: Tab & Fig No 15:

Only 24% of patients are keeping records of blood pressure after checking their blood pressure.76% are not keeping their blood pressure records

Table 16

Q8: Has your doctor or any health professional advised you to check your blood pressure regularly at home?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid yes	30	60.0	60.0	60.0
no	20	40.0	40.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Explanation: Tab & Fig No 16:

60% patients agreed that Doctors advised them to check regularly at home but 40% answered that no body advised them to check blood pressure at home regularly.

Table 17

Q9: Have you ever checked your blood cholestrol level with in last three months?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid yes	15	30.0	30.0	30.0
no	35	70.0	70.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Explanation: Tab & Fig No 17:

Only 30% of patients have checked their blood cholesterol level in the last three months but 70% have did not checked their cholesterol level in the last three months.

Table 18

Q10: have you ever been informed by any health professional or doctor that cholesterol level is higher than normal?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid yes	6	12.0	12.0	12.0
no	44	88.0	88.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Explanation: Tab & Fig No 18:

Only 12% of patients known that their blood cholesterol level is high but most of the patients 88% have no information of cholesterol level that because of two reason one is that, they did not check blood cholesterol level and the second is that the doctor did not inform them about high or low cholesterol level.

Table 19

Q11: Do you feel that kidney disease also affects your blood pressure?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid yes	43	86.0	86.0	86.0
no	7	14.0	14.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Explanation: Tab & Fig No 19:

In this data 86% of patients agreed that high blood pressure have great effect on their kidney disease. High blood pressure have great role in kidney failure most of the patient accept that the renal failure main cause is the high blood pressure. While only 14% told that high blood pressure have no affect on kidney failure.

Table 20

Q12: Has your doctor advised you medicine for your high cholesterol level?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid yes	9	18.0	18.0	18.0
no	41	82.0	82.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Explanation: Tab & Fig No 20:

18% patient are taking medicines for high cholesterol level while 82% of patients are not taking any medication for cholesterol level. it is because of the doctor did not prescribe or the patients are unaware from high blood cholesterol level.

Table 21

Have you been smoke?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	yes	9	18.0	18.0	18.0
	no	41	82.0	82.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Explanation: Tab & Fig No 21:

18% of CRF patient are smoking but 82% patients are not smoking.

Table 22

Do you do any exercise daily?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid yes	34	68.0	68.0	68.0
no	16	32.0	32.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Explanation: Tab & Fig No 22:

68% of patients are doing exercise on daily basis and regularly but the 32% of patients are not doing any physical activity or exercise in daily life.

Table 23

Do you have any financial issue?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid yes	30	60.0	60.0	60.0
no	20	40.0	40.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Explanation: Tab & Fig No 23:

60% of patient have financial issues but 40% told that they have no financial issue

Table 24

Has high blood pressure any effect on your life style?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Yes	47	94.0	94.0	94.0
No	3	6.0	6.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Explanation: Tab & Fig No 24:

In this data 94% of patients agreed that life style become change after high blood pressure and great effect on their lifestyle but only 6% patient told that due to high blood pressure there is no any effect on life style.

Table No 25

Has your doctor put you on some dietary restriction?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	43	86.0	86.0	86.0
	No	7	14.0	14.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Explanation: Tab & Fig No 25:

86% patients accept that the doctors told them what to eat and what to do not eat and most of them are following these dietary restrictions. On the other hand 14% of patients told that there is no dietary restriction on them from their doctor's sides. They are eating everything as they want.

Table NO 26

Do you feel that high blood pressure increase your stress?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Yes	47	94.0	94.0	94.0
No	3	6.0	6.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Explanation: Tab & Fig No 26:

In this results 94% of patient agree that increased their stress while only 6% patients told that blood pressure did not increases their stress.

Table No 27

Do you have any other disease which may be relates to your high blood pressure?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Yes	33	66.0	66.0	66.0
No	17	34.0	34.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Explanation: Tab & Fig No 27:

66% of patients have other diseases which relates to blood pressure and 34% patients told that they don't have any other disease which we can relate with the high blood pressure.

Table No 28

Is there any history of hypertension in your family?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	36	72.0	72.0	72.0
	No	14	28.0	28.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Explanation: Tab & Fig No 28:

In this data the 72% of patients have family history of hypertension while the 28% patient have no family history of hypertension.

Demographic data table 1

S no	Demographic	Frequency	Percentage
1	Age		
	17 to 37	17	34%
	38 to 57	21	42%
	58 to 87	12	24%
	Total	50	100%
2	Gender		
	Male	25	50%
	Female	25	50%
	Total	50	100%
3	Marital status		
	Married	46	92%
	Unmarried	4	8%
	Total 50	50	100%
4	Ward/Department		
	Nephro ward	48	96%
	Isolation department	2	4%
	Total	50	100%
5	Literate	15	30%
	Illiterate	35	70%
	Total	50	100%

6	Qualification		
	Primary to matric	9	18%
	Intermediate	4	8%
	Graduate to master	2	4%
	Illiterate	35	70%
	Total	50	100%
7	Occupation		
	House wife	23	46%
	On service	22	44%
	Jobless	5	10%
	Total	50	100%
8	Diagnoses		
	CRF	11	22%
	CRF.HTN	29	58%
	CRF.HTN.DM	10	20%
	Total	50	100%

Statistic results of questioner table 2

S.No	Question	Yes %	No %
Q.1	Have you diagnose by any health professional or doctor that you have blood pressure?	76%	24%
Q.2	Are you told by your doctor about your hypertension on regular visits?	60%	40%
Q.3	Do you feel that your job is one of the major causes of your blood pressure?	56%	44%
Q.4	BP of the patient at the time of data collection. 1. High blood pressure 2. Low blood pressure BP ranges SBP normal 120 to 140 and DBP normal 80 to 90 if the BP low or high from these ranges will be consider abnormal.	76%	24%
Q.5	Are you taking any prescribed medicine for hypertension?	86%	24%
Q.6	Have you ever checked your blood pressure at home during rest time in last three months?	64%	36%
Q.7	Do you checked your blood pressure regularly and keep record?	24%	76%
Q.8	Has your doctor or any health professional advised you to check your blood pressure regularly at home?	60%	40%
Q.9	Have you ever checked your blood cholesterol level with in last three months?	30%	70%
Q.10	Have you ever been informed by any health professional or doctor that your cholesterol level is higher than normal?	12%	88%
Q.11	Do you feel that kidney disease also affects your blood pressure?	86%	14%

Q.12	Has your doctor advised you medicine for your high cholesterol level?	18%	82%
Q.13	Have you been smoking?	18%	82%
Q.14	Do you do any exercise daily?	68%	32%
Q.15	Do you have any financial issue?	60%	40%
Q.16	Has high blood pressure any effect on your life style?	94%	6%
Q.17	Has your doctor put you on some dietary restriction?	86%	14%
Q.18	Do you feel that high blood pressure increase your stress?	94%	6%
Q.19	Do you have any other disease which may be relates to your high blood pressure?	66%	34%
Q.20	Is there any history of hypertension in your family?	72%	28%

Discussion chapter 5:

This chapter will discuss the study results and their implications. Moreover this study was an effort to highlight the main factors that lead to the prevalence of hypertension among CRF patients. And to Identifying major risk factors on the onset of CRF is an important part in preventing complications of developing hypertension in kidney failure patients.

Discussion of main results:

In this study the sample consisted of 50% males, and 50% females. The mean age for males was 40.0 years, while the females mean age was 42.0. These results agree with several international studies that were conducted in Japan, France, Iran, and Korean showed that HTN and CRF dramatically increases with aging, particularly after the age of 50 in both genders and males develop CRF more than females (Reza A, 2007), (Jungers P, et al, 1996) (Nagata M, et al, 2010), (Yu M, Ryu S, et al, 2010). Less than half (46.7 %) of the sample reported a HTN of 25-29.9 which make them in the category of overweight and 7.7% were reported as being obese. This result indicates that the majority of the study participants were suffering from increasing weight. Studies conducted in USA showed that there is positive association between BMI and CRF (Vupputuri S, et al, 2003). 59 Patients who have a regular habit of smoking composed (58.7%) of study sample, the percentage of male smokers was 58.36, while female smokers were only (0.34%). this results can be

explained that smoking as a habit in Pakistani society is not accepted for females. Studies show that there is no association smoking on the onset of HTN. Several other studies conducted in USA, Singapore, Norway, Germany, Italy and Austria showed that obesity and smoking are important independent risk factors for chronic kidney failure and HTN. (Vupputuri S, et al, 2003) (Friedman. E. 2001) (Chi-yuan H, et al, 2009) (Stein H, et al , 2006) (Shankar A, et al, 2008) (Hsu CY, et al, 2009) (Charles E, et al, 2006) Such differences between the current study and other studies on the impact of variables of gender and age could be due to genetic or social differences between Palestine community and other communities. The majority of participants are unemployed. This is a normal result since most of study sample were either old or (age mean = 40.0-41.0 years). CRF was less prevalent among refugee camps with a percentage of (8.2%), this can be explained that refugee camps represent a small section of the total Palestinian population, while CRF was more common among village residents with a percent of (59.4%) this is due to the fact that Rural area explained that large section of total Pakistani population and most health canter concentrated in cities. The results that there is no effect of gender, smoking, BMI, and work statues none of the factors had any significant relation to the onset of CRF.

The study results indicates that HTN patients who have a family member's history of HTN has a highest

probability of developing CRF. This means that patients with positive family history members with hypertension are more likely to have chronic kidney disease than other disease. The study results indicates that HTN patients who have a family members history with HTN has a high probability of developing HTN was (details) this means that HTN patients who have family members with HTN exerts positive significant effect on onset of CRF in patients. The study results indicates that HTN patients who have a family members history with diabetes reached (odds ratio = 1.7), that means the patients has positive family history members with diabetes (1.7) times more likely to have HTN as those who had no diabetes. Study found that HTN patients with family history members with cardiovascular disease reached an odds ratio of (1.4) this means that cardiovascular disease exerts positive significant effect on onset of HTN in patients. Study found that CRF patients with family history members with hypertension history played no significant association with onset CRF since odds ratio less than one (odds ratio= 0.96). 61 We can see that family members with a medical history of positive renal disease and HTN are more likely to develop CRF, this can be explained on the light of genetic factors can play a role in progressive renal failure. Furthermore, this result agree with other studies conducted in the USA that indicates an association between family history and incidence of HTN. (Freedman BI, et al, 2008) 5.1.3 Discussion of the Part Three: Study results indicate that the distribution of study sample according to chronic diseases such as (diabetes mellitus=46.4%), (Hypertension = 50.8%), lack of awareness among the people of the seriousness of kidney infections and urinary tract, as well as the recurrence of inflammatory. Some doctors do not order the necessary tests that is related to the of the kidney functions prior to prescribe the correct medication.

Ages of the patients

In this research the most of population ages 21 patients 42% of the data between in 38 years to 57 years the other patient between 17 years to 37 years 17 in numbers and 34% and ages of 12 patients are between 58 to 87 years 24% of the 100% of data. Here we make three categories and analyse the age distribution in it. Most of the patient's ages are between 37 years to 58 years the mean of ages is 40. studies shows in the world that hypertension and

chronic kidney diseases are increase in old ages. A descriptive study conducted in Iran showed that the prevalence of chronic renal failure (CRF) is high in Iran. The age group with high risk of CRF is (61-75) years old which constitute 38.5% (Reza A, 2007).

Gender of population

we collects data from 50 samples 100% patients which included 50% male and 50%female 25 samples of male and 25 samples of females.in world studies we have seen that there is no gender difference in the prevalence of HTN and CRF both diseases. Because the ratio of these diseases are same in both gender that's why we choose 50% male and 50% female patients for data collection. A cross-sectional study was conducted in Korea. Showed that the prevalence of chronic renal failure (CRF) increases with ageing. Particularly after (50) years in both genders (Yu M, et al, 2010)

Marital status

In this study we studied that 46 patients are married which is 96% of our population and only 4 patient 8% patients are unmarried this is because of the high prevalence rate of hypertension and chronic kidney disease in old ages A Prospective study conducted in French urban area showed incidence of CRF and HTN in males and a dramatic increase of incidence with age in both genders (Jungers P, et al, 1996).

Ward /isolation department

The data from ward of IKD is high because we choose convenient sampling in the ward we collect data from 48 patients 96% and from the isolation department we collect data from only 2 patients which is 4% of our data.

Literate /illiterate

Most of the patients are illiterate because all the patients belong from rural areas and in the rural areas the education ratio is less in Pakistan as consider to the urban areas of Pakistan. Only 30% of the patients are literate and 70% are illiterate. (Jungers P, et al, 1996).

Occupation

In 100% data the 46% are house wives 44% patients are on job and working in different organizations (government, private, semi private) and 10% of population is jobless and most of them are unable to

do work due to their old ages or due to the sever sickness of the diseases.

Diagnoses

The analyses of our population diseases in which we divided in three categories in first one we keep only CRF patients which is 22% the CRF and HTN both disease to which population in our study is 58% of the data and the patients who have multiple disease include CRF, HTN and DM are 20% of our population. The rationale of this variation is the ages of the patient who have HTN and CRF are between 38 and 57 years of ages. And in this age the prevalence of HTN is high (Jungers P, et al, 1996).

Discussion of Part Two:

The study results indicates that HTN patients who have a family member's history of HTN has a highest probability of developing CRF. This means that patients with positive family history members with hypertension are more likely to have chronic kidney disease than other disease. The study results indicates that HTN patients who have a family members history with HTN has a high probability of developing HTN was (details) this means that HTN patients who have family members with HTN exerts positive significant effect on onset of CRF in patients. The study results indicates that HTN patients who have a family members history with diabetes reached (odds ratio = 1.7), that means the patients has positive family history members with diabetes (1.7) times more likely to have HTN as those who had no diabetes. Study found that HTN patients with family history members with cardiovascular disease reached an odds ratio of (1.4) this means that cardiovascular disease exerts positive significant effect on onset of HTN in patients. 61 We can see that family members with a medical history of positive renal disease and HTN are more likely to develop CRF, this can be explained on the light of genetic factors can play a role in progressive renal failure. Furthermore, this result agree with other studies conducted in the USA that indicates an association between family history and incidence of HTN. (Freedman BI, et al, 2008)

Discussion of the Part Three:

Study results indicate that the distribution of study sample according to chronic diseases such as (hypertension and diabetes mellitus with CRF=20%), (Hypertension with CRF= 58%), and

(only CRF founded 22%) lack of awareness among the people of the seriousness of kidney infections and urinary tract, as well as the recurrence of inflammatory. Some doctors do not order the necessary tests that is related to the of the kidney functions prior to prescribe the correct medication.

Have you diagnose by any health professional or doctor that you have blood pressure?

In our study 76% of the participant were diagnosed as hypertensive before chronic renal failure disease. While 24% participants in our study did not diagnosed as hypertensive by any Doctor or health care professional because these undiagnosed patients did not check their blood pressure reading before kidney failure. In data collection most of the undiagnosed patients were unaware of hypertensive disease.

Are you told by your doctor about your hypertension on regular visits?

In this data study result shows that 60% of the patients were aware from hypertension as their disease and their doctors told them clearly in during several visits to clinics or Hospitals. While 40% of the patients were not told by their doctors about their hypertension on regular basis. That's why some of the patients were unaware from hypertension precautions.

Do you feel that your job is one of the major causes of your blood pressure?

Prevalence is 56% of the study population agreed that their job or work environment is also one of the major cause of hypertension. This is due to multiple problems at job place which included work load, transport problems, noise, pollution congested environment and unsatisfactory job. But on other hand 44% of patients told that there is no role of job in hypertension. Job did not cause any hypertension.

BP of the patient at the time of data collection.

BP ranges SBP normal 120 to 140 and DBP normal 80 to 90 if the BP low or high from these ranges will be consider abnormal.

In this study the prevalence of hypertension is 76% and normal population is 24%. Because we checked the blood pressures reading of our patients at the time of questioners in every department. The results shows that the blood pressure of 76% of population

recorded high. While 24% of the patient's blood pressure normally recorded in the hospital. First we finalized a criteria for high blood pressure and normal blood pressure. Blood pressure has been noted as high prevalence rate in world wide.

Study conducted in Egypt showed that hypertension was responsible for (28%) of the cases of renal failure in Egypt. Other significant causes were: chronic Glomerulonephritis (16.6%), ESRD of unknown etiology (16.2%), obstructive uropathy (9.3%), and diabetic nephropathy (8.9%) (Afifi A, 1999).

This study shows prevalence of hypertension is 28% and other disease are less involve in the renal failure.

Are you taking any prescribed medicine for hypertension?

The prevalence of those participants who are taking medicines for high blood pressure are 86% and they are taking medicines as advised. While the 14% of population told that their doctors did not prescribed any medicines to them for hypertension.

Have you ever checked your blood pressure at home during rest time in last three months?

In 100% population 64% of patients are checking their blood pressure at home and they checked it in the last three months but on the other hand 36% of the patients are not checking their blood pressure readings at home they also did not check blood pressure reading at least one time in last three months.

Has your doctor or any health professional advised you to check your blood pressure regularly at home?

The overall prevalence of participants who were advised to check blood pressure readings at home are 60% of the population and advised in prior by doctor to check blood pressure regularly while 40% of population did not advised by any health professional or doctor to check blood pressure regularly.

Have you ever checked your blood cholesterol level with in last three months?

During this study we identified that most of the patients are unaware from their laboratory test especially blood cholesterol level. In 100% patients 70% of the patients did not check their blood cholesterol level and only 30% checked cholesterol with in last three months.

Do you feel that kidney disease also affects your blood pressure?

In our study most of the patient (86%) believe that the kidney disease is the cause of high blood pressure this is because of these patients were diagnose as CRF.while the remaining 14% were not agree with this statement.

Have you been smoking?

Smoking is associated with an increased cardiac rate and (minimum) diastolic blood pressure, and the study showed that smokers have a six times reduced elastic capacity in their arterial system when compared to non-smokers, although this fact was not found to be statistically significant in the current study. This study reveal that 18% of patients involve in smoking while 82% of patients in smoking. Concerning the knowledge about measures and practices for the control of hypertension, there was no significant difference between genders. Lifestyle did not influence the knowledge about control measures of hypertension, but influenced its practice. It should be noted that smokers practice significantly less a low-salt diet and take less routine medication when compared to ex-smokers and non-smokers.

Do you do any exercise daily?

The overall prevalence of physical inactivity was 32%. And the 68% participants are doing some exercises/activities in daily life. Moreover In these 68% if we consider them 100%.Of the 100% who were physically active (44%) were general hand workers and the activity was experienced mainly at work. Only 23 (46%) participants do significant activity (more than 30 minutes of moderate or vigorous activity/day) at home or during leisure time and 5 (10%) participants have sedentary lifestyle.

Do you have any financial issue?

The overall prevalence of the financial issue is 60% seen in this study while 40% of the participant have no financial issue. The socioeconomic conditions analysed by educational levels and income per capita revealed a greater prevalence of hypertension among the CRF patients with lower educational levels and lower income and this association was also found in other studies. The educational levels may facilitate not only the acquisition of knowledge of better

control practices, but also better working opportunities and income.

Has high blood pressure any effect on your life style?

The effect of high blood pressure on the life style of this population is 94% which is very increase rate this means that most of the hypertensive patient's life style become changed after disease. In this study only the 6% patients life style were not affected due to hypertension.

Do you have any other disease which may be relates to your high blood pressure?

In the present study, the prevalence of chronic diseases drew attention since, although statistically significant, the number of chronic diseases reported was only higher among patients with hypertension when compared to those without hypertension who reported one or two diseases.

Is there any history of hypertension in your family?

The prevalence of family hypertension in this study is 72% recorded. While 28% patients have no family history of hypertension. The prevalence of hypertension in all over the world is due to the stress but the family history of hypertension has great role in the prevalence of HTN in the world. One hundred and fifty five (51.3%) participants had an immediate family member with a history of hypertension and 107 (69.0%) were females. Sixty four (40%) of the family members with a history of hypertension were mothers of participants. Fifty six (36%) of the family members with a history of hypertension had developed complications of hypertension such as heart failure (35/36), stroke (16/36) and kidney failure (9/36) (Stengel B .2003).

Have you diagnose by any health professional or doctor that you have blood pressure?

In our study 76% of the participant were diagnosed as hypertensive before chronic renal failure disease. While 24% participants in our study did not diagnosed as hypertensive by any Doctor or health care professional because these undiagnosed patients did not check their blood pressure reading before kidney failure. In data collection most of the undiagnosed patients were unaware of hypertensive disease.

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56% of the study population agreed that their job or work environment is also one of the major cause of hypertension. This is due to multiple problems at job place which included work load, transport problems, noise, pollution congested environment and unsatisfactory job. But on other hand 44% of patients told that there is no role of job in hypertension. Job did not cause any hypertension.

BP of the patient at the time of data collection. BP ranges SBP normal 120 to 140 and DBP normal 80 to 90 if the BP low or high from these ranges will be consider abnormal.

In this study the prevalence of hypertension is 76% and normal population is 24%. Because we checked the blood pressures reading of our patients at the time of questioners in every department. The results shows that the blood pressure of 76% of population recorded high. While 24% of the patient's blood pressure normally recorded in the hospital. First we finalized a criteria for high blood pressure and normal blood pressure. Blood pressure has been noted as high prevalence rate in world wide.

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This study shows prevalence of hypertension is 28% and other disease are less involve in the renal failure in the Egypt.

Conclusion & Recommendations chapter 6:

Prevalence of hypertension, with its high burden of CRF risk factors, represents an important public health concern. As the prevalence of high blood pressure present in the CRF patients. Moreover

hypertension have great effect on the lifestyle of these patients. The identification of an individual with hypertension should alert the practitioners to a large underlying burden of potentially modifiable hypertension risk factors. The study showed a significant association between a number of CRF risk factors and hypertension, such CRF risk factors include hypertension, diabetic mellitus, and increased total cholesterol, triglycerides, LDL, and decreased HDL, physical inactivity, stress. This positive association was shown in all patient of hypertension and chronic renal failure.

Some CRF risk factors revealed progressive nature such as hypertension, physical inactivity, dyslipidaemia, and diabetic mellitus, since these factors were increased as CRF progressed.

Other studied hypertension risk factors, including obesity, and family history of CVD, did not show statistically significant association with CRF in the patients of the study.

Recommendations

1. Regular evaluation of hypertension risk factors in CRF patients is needed for early diagnosis of these risk factors more over there is a need of educating the community on importance of lifestyle modification such as dietary modification and exercise so as to reduce the risks of hypertension, also to have habit of checking their blood pressures for early detection and treatment so as to avoid the complications of hypertension which are fatal.

2. Aggressive management of hypertension risk factors, especially modifiable risk factors such as sedentary life style , diet control stress, and physical inactivity in early stages, is important in controlling the disease progression and may reduce the hypertension events among CRF patients

3. Increase attention to hypertension events, even at early stages of CRF, not only by nephrologists, but more importantly by every health professional/doctors and the general medical community.

4. Encourage the general physicians and doctors for early diagnoses of the patients with primary kidney deterioration to the nephrology centres will enable early prevention of CRF and hypertension also.

5. Increase awareness of hypertension and its complications and methods of control and prevention, on the level of public community, is important in reducing its adverse consequences.

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Permission from the kidney center Hayat Abad medical Complex Peshawar

To

The chief executive/deputy medical superintendent Kidney center Hayat Abad medical complex Peshawar Khyber-Pakhtunkhwa Pakistan.

Subject: Request for permission for conducting a research study in the Hospital

Respected Madam,

With due request it is stated that we are conducting a research study in this hospital on the topic of prevalence of high blood pressure in the ARF/CRF patients. We will maintain the standard of Research ethics, and will not violate the environment of the hospital. So we request you to allow us to conduct this study in this institute

We shall be thankful to you for this act of kindness.

Yours obediently,
Amjid Ali and Mubashira Aman
Students of Post R.N 4th Semester,
Post Graduate College of nursing Peshawar.

Date: / /

Consent forms attached

Study title:

The prevalence of high blood pressure in ARF/CRF patients in Kidney center Hayat Abad Medical Complex Peshawar, KPK

Researcher: Amjid Ali and Mubashira Aman

We are the student of post RN BScN 4th semester program at Post Graduate College of nursing Peshawar, KPK.

We are conducting a study on prevalence of high blood pressure in ARF/CRF patients at Kidney center Hayat Abad Medical Complex Peshawar KPK Pakistan

The purpose of this study is to know the prevalence of high blood pressure in ARF/CRF patients at Kidney center Hayat Abad Medical Complex Peshawar KPK Pakistan

Participant (patient) is given the right to participate voluntary in the study and reserve the right to withdraw his or herself from this study at any time. Confidentiality of the data will be maintained and the identity will not be disclosed in any phase of the study. Participant will be assigned a code that will be known by the researcher only and after the completion of the study the participant will be explained or given the result of the study.

I have read the above detail and I am willing to participate in this study.

Patient Name _____

Patient signature _____

This study has been explain to the concerned participant and his/her voluntarily consent has been taken .if you have any quire than you will be contact on this number 0334 9274969 any time.

Researcher

Date

Questioner:

Prevalence of high blood pressure and quality of life among CRF patients at kidney entre Hayat Abad Peshawar.

A project of post graduate college of nursing Hayatabad Peshawar

Patient's name:	Ward: literate/ illiterate	Bed number:	Qualification:
Age SEX:	Occupation:	Date of Admission:	
Marital status	Residence:	Diagnoses:	
S NO	Question		
Q.01	Have you diagnose by any health professional or doctor that you have blood pressure? 1. YES <input type="checkbox"/> 2. NO <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q.02	Are you told by your doctor about your hypertension on regular visits? 1. YES <input type="checkbox"/> 2. NO <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q.03	Do you feel that your job is one of the major causes of your blood pressure? 1. YES <input type="checkbox"/> 2. NO <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q.04	Bp of the patient at the time of data collection. 3. High blood pressure BP / mmhg 4. Low blood pressure BP / mmhg *BP ranges SBP normal 120 to 140 and DBP normal 80 to 90 if the BP low or high from these ranges will be consider abnormal.		
Q.05	Are you taking any prescribed medicine for hypertension? 1. YES <input type="checkbox"/> 2. NO <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q.06	Have you ever checked your blood pressure at home during rest time in last three months? 1. YES <input type="checkbox"/> 2. NO <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q.07	Do you checked your blood pressure regularly and keep record? 1. YES <input type="checkbox"/> 2. NO <input type="checkbox"/>		

Q.08	Has your doctor or any health professional advised you to check your blood pressure regularly at home? 1. YES <input type="checkbox"/> 2. No <input type="checkbox"/>
Q.09	Have you ever checked your blood cholesterol level with in last three months? 1. YES <input type="checkbox"/> 2. NO <input type="checkbox"/>
Q.10	Have you ever been informed by any health professional or doctor that your cholesterol level is higher than normal? 1. YES <input type="checkbox"/> 2. NO <input type="checkbox"/>
Q.11	Do you feel that kidney disease also affects your blood pressure? 1. yes <input type="checkbox"/> 2. No <input type="checkbox"/>
Q.12	Has your doctor advised you medicine for your high cholesterol level? 1. YES <input type="checkbox"/> 2. NO <input type="checkbox"/>
Q.13	Have you been smoking? 1. YES <input type="checkbox"/> 2. NO <input type="checkbox"/>
Q.14	Do you do any exercise daily? 1. YES <input type="checkbox"/> 2. NO <input type="checkbox"/>
Q.15	Do you have any financial issue? 1. YES <input type="checkbox"/> 2. NO <input type="checkbox"/>
Q.16	Has high blood pressure any effect on your life style? 1. YES <input type="checkbox"/> 2. NO <input type="checkbox"/>
Q.17	Has your doctor put you on some dietary restriction? 1. YES <input type="checkbox"/> 2. NO <input type="checkbox"/>
Q.18	Do you feel that high blood pressure increase your stress? 1. YES <input type="checkbox"/> 2. NO <input type="checkbox"/>

Q 19	Do you have any other disease which may be relates to your high blood pressure? 1. YES <input type="checkbox"/> 2. NO <input type="checkbox"/>
Q. 20	Is there any history of hypertension in your family? 1.YES <input type="checkbox"/> 2.NO <input type="checkbox"/>

